

The Agrarian Bosons and the Direction Invariant Fermion Distributions - 8T

O Manor

August 10, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T, a varying Lorentz manifold with arbitrary variation that vanish into matter, and Bosons as net variation/curvature of discrete amounts, as given by the primordial coupling series, it is possible to present Bosons as violations of stationarity. The configuration of the matter on the manifold is a clear cutting indication to places in which those "agrarian" Bosons appeared. Since Bosons propagation is invariant to direction, the universe must look the same in all directions.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. The sole mathematical discipline of the 8T is calculus of variations. As reader assumed familiar with it, one of the major features of this theory is the vanishing of variation.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\delta q_i} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial q_i} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{q}_i} \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) = 0$$

Since in our theory we have the arbitrary variation term in equation (1.48) to vanish into matter, we can represent the idea as:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\delta g_i} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial g_i} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{g}_i} \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) = 0 \quad (1.8)$$

If so, Bosons as net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers are interfering with the stationarity of the manifold, hence their name "Agrarian", as they cannot vanish into matter, they cause the matter clustering. For Bosons:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\delta g_i} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial g_i} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{g}_i} \left(\frac{d}{dt} \right) > 0 \quad (1.81)$$

One final point, since the primorial coupling series is invariant to direction:

$$\mathcal{P}_0 = 8 + (1)$$

$$\mathcal{P}_N \# = \left(2^{\mathcal{M}} * \prod_{V=1}^{V=N} \mathcal{P}_V + (\mathcal{M}) \right) + \mathcal{P}_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.2.A)$$

As presented in the idea of probability variation of the (1.2A):

$$P_A \# = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) + \mathcal{M} \right) + P(A) \quad (3.3)$$

$$A \in \mathbb{P};$$

The matter configuration of the manifold should invariant to direction, that is precisely because it is not possible to determine where the lepton is going to emit or absorb, or even which kind of bosons are in play. Put another way, because it is impossible to know where the net curvature that violate stationarity will appear, the fermion distribution across all directions of the manifold is the same, there is no special direction of any sort. That is precisely the current modern picture of cosmology, the universe look everywhere the same. Same idea we presented in earlier paper of the sphere shape of starts, but now to much larger Fermion clusters.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

o.m